

Wide Range Variation of $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ Isotopes in the Çayırhan Oil Shales: Multiple Sulfur Sources and Environmental Influences

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Abstract

Geochemical and mineralogical analyses of the Miocene-aged Çayırhan Oil Shales (ÇOS) reveal a significant presence of sulfur, particularly abundant framboidal pyrite. The formation of framboidal pyrite typically occurs in reducing, sulfur-rich, and microbially active environments, indicating such conditions prevailed during deposition. Sulfur isotope analyses ($\delta^{34}\text{S}$) of 25 samples show a wide range of values, from -6.37‰ to $+26.55\text{‰}$, with an average of $+13.86\text{‰}$. This broad range suggests the involvement of multiple sulfur sources, including marine sulfate, freshwater sulfate (potentially through plant uptake), and hydrothermal sulfur. Low $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values point to microbial sulfate reduction and freshwater influence, while high values may reflect closed-system conditions or rapid sedimentation. Since framboidal pyrite generally forms via microbial sulfate reduction and subsequent FeS_2 precipitation, its presence in ÇOS strongly supports a biogenic origin. The wide $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ variation further indicates that environmental factors such as pH and oxygen fugacity ($f\text{O}_2$) influenced pyrite formation. According to the literature, positive $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values are often linked to slight pH drops, while negative values are associated with higher $f\text{O}_2$ levels. In summary, framboidal pyrite formation in the Çayırhan Basin was controlled by a complex interplay of diverse sulfur sources and varying environmental conditions. The isotopic variability reflects both open and closed system behavior in a lacustrine setting, influenced by microbial activity, diagenesis, redox conditions, sedimentation rates, and pH changes.

Keywords: Framboidal pyrite, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ isotope, sulfur fractionation, oxygen fugacity ($f\text{O}_2$), pH

1. Introduction

Pyrite framboids are among the most striking morphological forms of pyrite, typically appearing as microscopic, raspberry-shaped aggregates composed of spheroidally arranged, euhedral microcrystals. These structures are commonly observed in organic-rich sedimentary environments such as mudstones, coals, shales, and related deposits (Rickard, 1969a; Wilkin and Barnes, 1996). Although the direct role of microorganisms in framboid formation still debated among researchers, several studies suggest a link between these structures and microbial mats (Goldhaber and Kaplan, 1974; Kohn et al., 1998). Framboid formation is often associated with microenvironments that develop at water-gas (notably H_2S and CO_2) interfaces in clay-rich sediments or FeS -rich detrital muds. These environments are typically characterized by low temperatures, low salinity, bicarbonate saturation, and the presence of reduced sulfur species such as hydrogen sulfide, thiosulfate, and elemental sulfur (Rickard, 1970; Wilkin and Barnes, 1997). These chemical and physical parameters are critical in guiding microbial activity and mineralization pathways. The morphology of framboids including their nucleation, crystal growth, and spherical arrangement appears to be shaped by the specific conditions of microbial sediment formation. Sulfur isotope data provide further support for a biogenic origin, as microbial sulfur fractionation typically results in more pronounced isotopic fractionation compared to abiotic processes (Kohn et al., 1998; Anderson et al., 1987; Ferris et al., 1989). Indicators of biologically mediated pyritization include similarities in grain size between FeS and FeS_2 framboids, narrow distributions of sulfur and ferrous iron, low numbers of large crystals within framboids, and specific sulfur isotope fractionations between H_2S and FeS_2 ranging from -11.14‰ to -16.24‰ (Kohn et al., 1998; Fisher and Hudson, 1987). Such geochemical and morphological signatures strongly point to biologically influenced pyrite formation. Framboidal pyrite is not only valuable for understanding geochemical processes but also holds significance for identifying microbial

influences, tracing past biological activity (paleomicrobiology), and even investigating potential biosignatures on other planets (astrobiology) (Love and Amstutz, 1966; Popa et al., 2004). Biomineralization defined as the biologically mediated formation of inorganic minerals has been observed across nearly all branches of life and accounts for over sixty known biogenic minerals (Lowenstam, 1981). Biogenic iron sulfides such as greigite (Fe_3S_4) and pyrite (FeS_2) play key roles in global iron and sulfur cycling (Postgate, 1963). Bacteria contribute to the formation of iron sulfide minerals through both passive biomineralization and biologically controlled processes (Heywood et al., 1990; Konhauser, 1997). Mineral formation via biomineralization is heavily dependent on environmental conditions. For instance, H_2S produced by cells or introduced from external solutions can readily react with dissolved iron or bind to negatively charged bacterial surfaces, leading to monosulfide ($\text{H}_2\text{S} + \text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{FeS} + \text{H}_2$) or disulfide ($2\text{H}_2\text{S} + \text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{FeS}_2 + 2\text{H}_2$) formation (Rickard, 1969b; Krouse and McCready, 1979). Although the precipitation of iron sulfides is often enhanced by microbial presence, the process itself is passive and the resulting crystal structures can resemble those of abiotic origin (Lowenstam, 1981). Biological pathways in iron sulfide formation include microbial sulfate reduction, anaerobic degradation of sulfur bearing organics, and iron respiration (Koch, 1985; Ferris et al., 1989; Canfield et al., 1998). In biologically controlled biomineralization, microorganisms can influence the type of mineral formed (Krouse and McCready, 1979). These processes are generally organism-directed, although their mechanisms are still not fully understood. Lowenstam (1981) proposed that an organic matrix is first produced, into which target ions are incorporated, initiating mineral crystallization. Such products often deviate from standard crystal structures and may exhibit lower solubility, isotopic separation, and trace element imbalances. Some microorganisms synthesize iron sulfide minerals like greigite for specific biological functions such as magnetotaxis (Mann, et al.,

1990; Bazylinski et al., 1995). However, the functional role of pyrite remains unclear. The biogenic formation of pyrite has been hypothesized to relate to energy metabolism in early life under the "iron-sulfur world" hypothesis, where pyrite formation could have been sufficiently exergonic to couple with ATP synthesis or reduction of NAD(P) (Wächtershäuser, 1990). Nonetheless, no current microbial species have been found to utilize this process as a direct energy source (Kohn et al., 1998). Framboids typically composed of pyrite have been reported in a variety of settings including sediments, limestones, soils, volcanic sequences, peats, fossil wood, and even ancient books (Love and Amstutz, 1966; Garcia-Guinea et al., 1997). While many framboids may form through abiotic pathways, their frequent occurrence just below redox boundaries supports a microbial origin (Goldhaber and Kaplan, 1974; Beveridge et al., 1983; Kohn et al., 1998). Framboid crystal arrangement appears to be governed primarily by the physical properties of the crystals themselves, independent of external controls (Rickard, 1970). Physical forces such as van der Waals attractions and Coulomb repulsion, as well as salinity, are believed to influence this organization. The origin of the spherical shape remains debated, with hypotheses suggesting replacement of pre-existing biological or colloidal structures. Proposed templates include microbial cells (Schneiderhöhn, 1923), amorphous FeS gels (Love and Amstutz, 1966), humic globules (Papunen, 1966), gas vacuoles or sulfur grains (Graham and Ohmoto, 1994), clay particles (Graham and Robertson, 1995), magnetically assembled greigite framboids (Schoonen and Barnes, 1991; Wilkin and Barnes, 1997), or greigite spheres replaced by pyrite (Popa et al., 2004). However, none of these hypotheses fully account for the consistent spherical morphology observed across diverse environments. Sulfur isotope fractionation serves as a valuable tool for identifying microbial roles in geochemical processes. Microorganisms tend to preferentially utilize

lighter isotopes, leaving characteristic isotopic signatures (Krumbein, 1983; Kohn et al., 1998). Whereas abiotic fractionation between SO_4^{2-} and FeS_2 typically ranges from -12% to -22% , microbial processes may produce much larger differences, from -40% to -60% (Anderson et al., 1987; Ferris et al., 1989; Fisher and Hudson, 1987; Kohn et al., 1998). These findings suggest microbial influence not only during sulfate reduction but also in the final stages of pyrite formation from H_2S .

2. Material and Methods

This study employed a multidisciplinary approach to investigate the Çayırhan Oil Shales (ÇOS). A total of 27 samples were collected from various stratigraphic levels during fieldwork. For petrographic analysis, both thin and polished sections were prepared. Thin sections were produced at the Department of Geological Engineering, Ankara University, while polished sections were embedded in 3 cm epoxy-mounted bakelite molds and polished using diamond abrasive discs at Yozgat Bozok University. The sections were examined using a Leica DM2500 polarizing microscope to determine mineral paragenesis, textural features, and mineral associations. To investigate the morphology and microstructural characteristics of pyrite and associated minerals, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) coupled with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) was conducted on 25 selected samples using a JEOL-JMS 6490 LV system. Additionally, sulfur isotope compositions were analyzed on 40 powdered samples at Iso-Analytical Laboratories (UK). The $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ measurements were performed using a Thermo Quest Finnigan Delta Plus XL continuous-flow isotope ratio mass spectrometer, with an analytical precision of $\pm 0.15\%$. These comprehensive analyses enabled a detailed understanding of the geochemical, mineralogical, and isotopic properties of the ÇOS units (Table 1).

Table 1. Çayırhan Oil Shales (ÇOS) – Applied Analyses and Number of Samples

Type of analysis	Number of samples	Purpose
XRD (X-ray Diffraction) Analysis	56	Identification of mineralogical composition
Petrographic Examination (Thin and Polished Sections)	27	Determination of mineral paragenesis and textural features
SEM-EDS (Scanning Electron Microscopy with EDS)	25	Investigation of mineral morphology, grain size, and inter-mineral relationships
$\delta^{34}\text{S}$ Sulfur Isotope Analysis	40	Determination of sulfur sources and formation mechanisms of framboidal pyrite

3. Geologic setting and stratigraphy

The study area, located northeast of Çayırhan and west of Beypazarı, lies within a ~30 km² portion of the Bolu H27-d sheet. The regional stratigraphy begins with the Paleocene-aged Kızılbayır Formation and is unconformably overlain by Middle Miocene sedimentary units namely the Boyalı, Hırka, Karadoruk, and Sariağıl formations intruded locally by Teke volcanics. These units subsequently overlain by the Pliocene Softa Formation and Quaternary alluvium. The oil shale deposits investigated in this study are hosted within the Hırka Formation, which exhibits both lateral and vertical facies transitions and conformably overlies the Boyalı Formation. Near Hırka village, this formation includes laminated sandstone, claystone, oil shale, carbonaceous shale, dolomitic limestone, tuff, and trona. The oil shales, typically gray to brown in color and 8–22 meters thick, are finely bedded and interlayered with dolomitic limestone and tuff, reflecting deposition in a lacustrine environment periodically influenced by volcanic activity (Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011).

4. Discussion

4.1. Mineralogical analyses

Mineralogical and textural analyses provide critical insights into mineral identification, the differentiation between diagenetic and detrital phases, quantitative mineral abundances,

mineral chemistry, and the nature and scale of porosity. Within the scope of this study, oil shale samples were examined through thin and polished section analyses to determine their mineralogical and textural characteristics. Additionally, X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy coupled with energy-dispersive spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) analyses were conducted to better assess the mineral content (Table 2). To best represent the vertical variation and overall mineralogical features of the oil shales, thin sections were prepared from 27 rock samples obtained from drill core "S" and examined under a polarizing microscope (Figures 1-4). These investigations allowed for the identification of mineral assemblages and the evaluation of textural and structural relationships. Photomicrographs were also taken at various scales from selected areas to document key features. Polished pellets were prepared from samples containing opaque minerals and examined using an ore microscope to determine ore paragenesis and infer physicochemical conditions of the depositional environment. Polished sections prepared to identify the opaque minerals within the Çayırhan Oil Shales revealed pyrite as the dominant phase under ore microscopic examination (Figures 5-8). Analysis of pyrite morphology indicates the presence of both euhedral and anhedral crystals, suggesting multiple generations of pyrite formation. This implies that pyrite developed during both early and late diagenetic stages within the formation.

Table 2. Applied mineralogical techniques and their analytical capabilities (Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011).

Technique	Mineral Identification	Distinction of Diagenetic vs. Detrital Phases	Mineral Quantification	Mineral Paragenesis	Mineral Chemistry	High-Resolution Textural and Mineralogical Analysis	Porosity Characterization
Polarizing Microscope	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Ore Microscope	✓	✓		✓			
SEM-EDS	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
XRD (Whole Rock)	✓						

Figure 1. Opaque Pyrite (Py) occurrences within Organic Matter (OM) observed in thin sections of S-6 sample

Figure 2. Opaque Pyrite (Py) occurrences within the Clay matrix (Cly) observed in thin sections of S-7 sample.

Figure 3. Flow structures observed in the Organic Matter (OM) and Clay (Cly) interlayers, as well as opaque Pyrite (Py) formations located between the layers in thin sections of S-62 sample.

Figure 4. Opaque Pyrite (Py) formations around Sanidine (Snd) crystals with radial crystal structure within the organic matter (OM) in thin sections of S-79 sample.

Figure 5. Disseminated and clustered Pyrites (Py) are observed between the oil shale layers in S-16 sample.

Figure 6. Radial and Spherical Pyrite (Py) crystals formed within the oil shales of S-69 sample.

Figure 7. The tips of radial sanidine crystals and the Pyrite (Py) crystals between them within the oil shales of S-78

Figure 8. Subhedral Pyrite (Py) crystals within the oil shales of S-15 sample.

4.2. XRD Analyses

The presence of pyrite has been identified among the whole-rock mineral components of each studied sample (Table 3). The dominant

mineral in the rocks is dolomite. In addition, XRD results revealed varying amounts of quartz, calcite, feldspar group minerals, micas, clays, pyrite, marcasite, and magnesite.

Table 3. XRD results of the Çayırhan oil shales (Pyrite was identified by XRD analysis in the following samples: B, C ÖSK units, CG gallery samples, and PK, PM, PR, PS, and S drill core samples; Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011).

Sample No	Pyrite	CG11	-	PM 2	+	S 4	+
B55	+	CG1	-	PR 31	+	S 5	+
B50	+	PK 26	-	PR 28	-	S 7	+
B46	+	PK 22	-	PR 25	+	S 14	+
B44	+	PK 19	-	PR 23	-	S 16	+
B42	+	PK 16	-	PR 22	+	S 17	+
B39	+	PK 14	+	PR 20	+	S 27	+
B37	+	PK 12	+	PR 17	+	S 54	+
B34	-	PK 10	+	PR 11	+	S 62	+
C33	+	PK 8	+	PR 7	-	S 63	+
C30	+	PK 5	+	PR 5	+	S 70	+
C28	+	PK 2	+	PR 4	-	S 72	+
C25	-	PK 1	+	PS 27	+	S 73	+
C21	+	PM 38	+	PS 19	+	S 74	+
C17	+	PM 34	+	PS 16	+	S 75	+
C15	+	PM 31	+	PS 14	+	S 76	+
C13	+	PM 28	+	PS 12	+	S 77	+
C11	+	PM 27	+	PS 10	+	S 78	+
C5	+	PM 24	+	PS 9	+	S83	+
CG 19	+	PM 21	+	PS 7	+		
CG15	-	PM 18	+	PS 3	+		
CG13	-	PM 17	+	PS 2	+		
		PM 13	+	PS 1	+		

4.3. Scanning electron microscopy – microanalysis (SEM-EDS)

Within the scope of this study, 25 SEM-EDS analyses were conducted. Pyrite crystals were identified in several samples, including PS 1 (Figure 9) and S 63 (Figure 10). The

chemical composition of the detected pyrite minerals was evaluated based on oxide forms, considering the elemental detection limits of the instrument. The results revealed high concentrations of specific element oxides (Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011).

Figure 9. Pyrite (Py) crystals identified by SEM-EDS analysis in PS-1 sample (Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011).

Figure 10. Pyrite (Py) crystal identified by SEM-EDS analysis in S-63 sample (Yavuz Pehlivanlı 2011).

4.4. Organic content and environmental conditions

The Çayırhan Oil Shales (ÇOS), part of the Middle Miocene-aged Hırka Formation, are characterized by high total organic carbon (TOC) content, ranging from 2.08% to 23.29%, with an average of 9.53%. These conditions suggest a favorable environment for sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB) to metabolize

sulfur. As noted in the literature (e.g., Goldhaber and Kaplan, 1974), SRBs can cause significant isotopic fractionation in the presence of abundant organic carbon and sulfate. Accordingly, the wide range of $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values observed in the ÇOS samples (from – 6.37‰ to +26.55‰, with an average of +13.86‰; Table 4) indicates active microbial sulfate reduction (Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011).

Table 4. Organic Geochemical Characteristics of the Çayırhan Oil Shales (ÇOS) (Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011).

Parameter		Value Range / Observations	Interpretation / Classification	Reference
TOC (Total Carbon)	Organic	2.08% – 48.48% (Average: 10.01%)	Very high organic matter content. Rich to excellent source rock potential	Tissot and Welte, 1984; Jarvie, 1991; Peters and Cassa, 1994
Kerogen Type		Mostly Type I; few samples Type II	Algal-derived organic matter suitable for oil generation	Espitalié et al., 1985
Organic Petrography		100% amorphous/algal organic matter	Liptinitic components favorable for oil generation	
Maturity (Tmax)		381 – 447°C	Most samples fall within the oil window; some are immature to early mature	Espitalié et al., 1985; Peters and Cassa, 1994
Hydrocarbon Potential (HC-TOC plot)	Potential	Classified as “very good” to “excellent”	High potential for oil and gas generation	Wehner, 1989
Genetic Potential (S1+S2)		1,770 – 198,490 ppm	Very good source rock potential	Tissot and Welte, 1984

4.5. Interpretation of $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values based on source

These findings indicate that the Çayırhan Oil Shales (ÇOS) have a high organic matter content, predominantly contain Type-I kerogen, and largely fall within the oil generation window in terms of thermal maturity. Based on both HC-TOC and genetic potential values, the ÇOS possess significant hydrocarbon generation potential. In the Çayırhan Oil Shales (ÇOS) samples, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values range from -6.37‰ to $+26.55\text{‰}$, with an average of $+13.86\text{‰}$ (Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011). These values indicate the influence of both open and closed system conditions during sulfur incorporation. High $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values ($\geq +20\text{‰}$) typically reflect closed system environments, characterized by limited sulfate diffusion and rapid sedimentation. In contrast, negative values (e.g., -6.37‰) suggest open system conditions with continuous sulfate replenishment, low sedimentation rates, or freshwater influence (Goldhaber and Kaplan, 1974; Ohmoto and Rye, 1979a) (Figure 11-12). When considered together with mineralogical, geochemical, and petrographic data, the isotopic composition of ÇOS samples points to biogenic sulfur sources and a lacustrine to continental depositional setting. In particular, the wide $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ range observed in samples from PS, PK, S, and B ÖSK implies the involvement of multiple sulfur sources. Environmental parameters such as pH and oxygen fugacity ($f\text{O}_2$) are also known to

influence $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values significantly. Lower pH conditions can lead to higher $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values, while elevated $f\text{O}_2$ tends to result in more negative values (Subías et al., 1997; Zhao et al., 2003). This suggests that the isotopic variability observed in the ÇOS samples is closely related to the chemical characteristics of the pore waters during formation. Although $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values of the samples overlap with both terrestrial and marine H_2S sources (Ohmoto and Goldhaber, 1997), previous studies, field observations, petrographic evidence, and elemental analyses from the study area support deposition in a continental lacustrine environment with a dominant contribution from organically derived SO_2 (Hoefs, 1996). The $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ isotopic values of the Çayırhan Oil Shales display a wide range, from approximately -6‰ to $+26\text{‰}$, indicating the influence of multiple sulfur sources and varying depositional conditions. When compared with global $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values from different geological environments such as marine sulfates, magmatic and sedimentary sulfides, and biogenic sulfur it becomes evident that the Çayırhan samples reflect both open and closed system sulfur dynamics. Samples from B, C, and CG generally show moderate $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values ($\sim +5\text{‰}$ to $+15\text{‰}$), while PK and PM extend to more positive values, nearing $+25\text{‰}$, suggesting closed system conditions or seawater sulfate input. In contrast, PS and S samples exhibit broader $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ ranges, from negative to highly positive values, pointing to the contribution of

biogenic sulfur and microbial sulfate reduction under fluctuating redox conditions. This isotopic variability, supported by petrographic and geochemical evidence, indicates a dominantly lacustrine-terrestrial setting influenced by both microbial activity and variable sedimentation rates. Sulfur compounds formed in different geological and environmental settings can be characterized by distinct $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ ranges. Sulfur sources related to urban atmospheric SO_2 and SO_4^{2-} , ore-forming processes, petroleum and natural gas systems, and coalification, typically associated with industrial or marine environments, generally exhibit positive $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values, usually ranging from 0‰ to +30‰ (Ohmoto and Rye, 1979a,b; Claypool et al., 1980; Ohmoto, 1986; Hoefs, 1996; Faure and Mensing, 2005; Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011; Ünal Çakır, 2020; Ünal Çakır, et al, 2023). In contrast, continental and marine environments where hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) is produced through bacterial sulfate reduction are typically characterized by more negative $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values, generally between -30‰

and 0‰. Sulfur derived from volcanic gases tends to have even lower isotopic values, sometimes reaching down to -40‰. In the Çayırhan region, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values obtained from the ÇOS samples range between -10‰ and +26‰. Higher $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values (e.g., above +15‰) are consistent with closed-system conditions, where sulfate diffusion is limited and microbial fractionation is minimal. These values are typically associated with environments where marine sulfate or atmospheric $\text{SO}_2/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ entered the sedimentary setting in restricted amounts. Conversely, lower $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values (e.g., below 0‰) reflect open-system conditions, where freshwater input and intense microbial sulfate reduction are more prominent. This isotopic diversity indicates the influence of multiple sulfur sources and variable redox conditions within the depositional basin (Ohmoto and Rye, 1979a,b; Claypool et al., 1980; Ohmoto, 1986; Hoefs, 1996; Faure and Mensing, 2005; Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011; Ünal Çakır, 2020).

Figure 11. $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ graphs of the çayırhan oil shales (Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011).

Figure 12. $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ (‰) Composition Histogram of the Çayırhan Oil Shales (ÇOS) (Yavuz Pehlivanlı, 2011).

4.6. Bacterial sulfate reduction and the possible mixing with marine sulfate

The $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ isotope data obtained from the Çayırhan Oil Shales do not fall below -10‰ , instead displaying a wide range between -6.37‰ and $+26.55\text{‰}$. This is noteworthy, as the lighter isotopic compositions typically expected from bacterial sulfate reduction (BSR) processes ranging from -20‰ to -40‰ are not observed. However, as emphasized in the literature (e.g., Canfield et al., 1998; Goldhaber & Kaplan, 1974), BSR under open-system conditions can lead to strong isotopic fractionation, whereas fractionation is more limited under closed-system settings. Therefore, the high $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values observed in the ÇOS samples may be attributed to restricted isotopic separation under closed-system conditions. In particular, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values exceeding $+20\text{‰}$ in some samples are consistent with the current isotopic composition of marine sulfate ($\sim +21\text{‰}$; Hoefs, 1996). This suggests that at least part of the sulfur present in ÇOS may have originated from the isochemical precipitation of marine sulfate. However, the isotopic composition may also have been partially modified by microbial processes, pointing to a scenario in which “sulfur reduced from marine sulfate” and “bacterially derived sulfur” are both contributing sources. On the other hand, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values decreasing to approximately -6‰ support open-system conditions where bacterial fractionation is

more effective, and/or contributions from freshwater-derived sulfate. This implies that both open and closed-system processes were active in different sedimentological environments and under variable redox conditions. Accordingly, the $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values in the samples reflect the influence of multiple sulfur sources within the Çayırhan Basin, including marine sulfate, atmospheric $\text{SO}_2/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$, and bacterially produced H_2S , resulting in a broad isotopic distribution. This complex isotopic pattern necessitates the integrated evaluation of several controlling factors, including the formation process of pyrite crystals, sedimentation rate, organic matter content, availability of reactive iron, pH, and oxygen fugacity. Thus, the $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values observed in the ÇOS cannot be attributed to a single mechanism but rather reflect an isotopic diversity shaped by the combined effects of multiple processes and sources.

5. Conclusion

Microscopic investigations, SEM-EDS, and sulfur isotope ($\delta^{34}\text{S}$) analyses conducted on the Çayırhan Oil Shales (ÇOS) have revealed that pyrite is a common diagenetic mineral throughout the formation. Pyrite occurrences are associated with both early and late diagenetic stages and exhibit various morphologies and elemental compositions. SEM-EDS analyses, highlighting significant Fe_2O_3 and SO_3 contents, support the formation

of pyrite under anoxic depositional conditions, characteristic of lacustrine or restricted basin settings (Emery and Robinson, 1993; Bazylinski et al., 1995). The $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values of analyzed samples range from -6.37‰ to $+26.55\text{‰}$, reflecting the influence of multiple geochemical processes and sulfur sources in the depositional environment. High $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values (e.g., $+20\text{‰}$ and above) are consistent with closed-system settings with limited sulfate diffusion and rapid sedimentation, while negative values indicate open systems, microbial sulfate reduction, and potentially freshwater sulfate input (Goldhaber and Kaplan, 1974; Jørgensen, 1979; Nielsen, 1979). In particular, low $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values point to microbial activity by sulfate-reducing bacteria such as *Desulfovibrio desulfuricans*, whereas intermediate to high values suggest the influence of transformed marine sulfate retained within sediments (Kaplan et al., 1963; Thode et al., 1960). The isotopic diversity is not solely related to source variability but also to physicochemical parameters of the depositional environment, such as pH, oxygen fugacity ($f\text{O}_2$), and redox conditions. Slightly acidic environments and reducing conditions are favorable for microbial sulfate reduction, often leading to heavier $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ signatures in closed systems (Subías et al., 1997; Fisher and Hudson, 1987; Zhao et al., 2003). Conversely, negative values are typically associated with more oxygenated zones or open systems with continuous sulfate renewal. The identification of framboidal pyrite in thin sections and SEM images further supports microbial sulfate reduction under anoxic conditions. These framboidal structures—commonly linked to biomineralization reflect microbially mediated precipitation processes and exhibit isotopic compositions consistent with microbial sulfur cycling (Lowenstam, 1981; Love and Amstutz, 1966; Graham and Ohmoto, 1994). The morphology and arrangement of microcrystals also suggest that physical forces (e.g., van der Waals or Coulomb interactions) and salinity played roles in framboid development (Rickard, 1970). Although framboidal textures are often interpreted as microbial in origin, isotopic fractionation data can more reliably

indicate their genesis. Microbial sulfate reduction is known to produce large fractionation effects, with $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ shifts of -40‰ to -60‰ , while abiotic processes usually result in narrower ranges (-12‰ to -22‰) (Ferris et al., 1989; Anderson et al., 1987). The $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values observed in the ÇOS samples fall within microbial fractionation ranges, thereby supporting a biogenic origin for much of the pyrite. The wide $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ variation observed in the Çayırhan Oil Shales reflects a complex interplay of sulfur sources and diagenetic processes under changing depositional conditions. This isotopic diversity, ranging from -10‰ to $+26\text{‰}$, indicates contributions from both marine-derived sulfate and bacterially reduced sulfur. Negative $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values suggest open-system conditions with freshwater input and active microbial sulfate reduction, whereas positive values point to closed-system environments with limited sulfate availability and restricted diffusion. These variations highlight dynamic redox conditions and the role of microbial activity in shaping the sulfur cycle. Overall, the data reveal how fluctuating geochemical environments in an anoxic, likely lacustrine setting influenced the formation and preservation of sulfur-bearing minerals, offering valuable insights into the paleoenvironmental evolution of the Çayırhan Basin and comparable sedimentary systems.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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